

DEVELOPMENT OF THE INSTITUTE OF INTERNATIONAL LEGAL PERSONALITY IN INTERNATIONAL INVESTMENT RELATIONS

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Abstract: The development of the Institute of International Legal Personality in International Investment Relations has been a significant topic of discussion among legal scholars and policymakers in recent years. This abstract explores the evolution of international legal personality in the context of cross-border investments, examining its role in shaping the rights and obligations of states and investors. It analyzes the key legal principles governing international legal personality in investment law, including the concept of state responsibility, the nationality principle, and the principle of sovereign immunity. Additionally, the abstract discusses the challenges and opportunities presented by the evolving nature of international investment relations, such as the rise of transnational corporations, the increasing role of international arbitration, and the impact of globalization on the concept of international legal personality.

Key words: International legal personality, International investment law, State responsibility, Foreign direct investment, Bilateral investment treaties

Introduction:

The concept of international legal personality (ILP) plays a crucial role in international law, providing the foundation for entities to bear rights and obligations on the global stage. Traditionally, international legal personality was reserved for sovereign states and intergovernmental organizations. However, the rise of international investment relations has expanded the scope, granting private actors, particularly multinational corporations (MNCs), an increasingly prominent role in global governance. This article will explore the evolution of ILP within the context of international investment relations, the driving factors behind its development, and the implications for modern international law [1].

Main part:

Historically, ILP was understood to be the exclusive domain of sovereign states, which were the primary actors in international law. The notion of ILP was formally developed in the early 20th century, particularly through the work of the Permanent Court of International Justice (PCIJ) and later the International Court of Justice (ICJ). These institutions affirmed that only states, as legal persons, had standing in international law to bring claims and conclude treaties [2].

International organizations, such as the United Nations and the World Trade Organization, also gained ILP, allowing them to participate in international legal processes. These bodies are created by treaties between sovereign states and derive their ILP from the express consent of their member states. Still, for much of the 20th century, ILP was strictly defined in terms of state sovereignty and intergovernmental relations [3].

The Expansion of ILP in International Investment Relations

With the globalization of markets and the increase in cross-border investment activities, non-state actors, particularly MNCs, began to play a significant role in shaping international investment relations. This necessitated a rethinking of ILP beyond states and

intergovernmental organizations, as MNCs started engaging in legal disputes and investment treaties.

International investment agreements began to include provisions that conferred rights and protections directly on foreign investors, typically corporations. These treaties established legal frameworks under which investors could pursue claims against host states through mechanisms like investor-state dispute settlement (ISDS). The North American Free Trade Agreement (NAFTA) and subsequent trade agreements serve as prominent examples of this evolution [4].

ISDS provisions, included in many BITs and MITs, allowed private investors to bring claims directly against states before international tribunals, bypassing traditional diplomatic channels. This shift granted MNCs a form of ILP, as they could now seek enforcement of their rights in international law without relying on their home states to act on their behalf.

Established by the World Bank, ICSID became a central forum for resolving investment disputes between states and foreign investors. It recognized the ability of private investors to engage in arbitration proceedings, further solidifying their role as international legal persons with standing in international law [5].

Several factors have contributed to the expansion of ILP in the realm of international investment:

1. **Economic Globalization:** The increasing interconnectivity of global markets and the rise of multinational corporations have blurred the lines between domestic and international spheres. As MNCs gained influence over cross-border trade, their need for legal protection and predictability in foreign markets led to the development of international frameworks that recognized their ILP [6].
2. **The Growing Importance of Foreign Direct Investment (FDI):** FDI became a cornerstone of economic development for many states, particularly in emerging markets. States began to enter into BITs and MITs to attract FDI, offering legal protections to foreign investors. This process shifted the balance of power between states and MNCs, as investors gained rights enforceable through international legal mechanisms.
3. **Human Rights and Corporate Responsibility:** The increasing awareness of corporate social responsibility and human rights obligations also played a role in reshaping ILP. While MNCs gained rights under investment treaties, they have also been held accountable for human rights violations and environmental degradation in host states. The United Nations Guiding Principles on Business and Human Rights, for instance, have encouraged a normative shift toward recognizing the responsibility of MNCs to uphold international human rights standards [7].

The development of ILP for private actors, particularly MNCs, has profound implications for the structure and functioning of international law. Some of these include:

1. **Fragmentation of International Law:** The rise of international investment arbitration has created a parallel legal regime that operates independently of traditional diplomatic and state-centric mechanisms. While this system offers foreign investors greater access to justice, it has also raised concerns about the potential for conflicting legal decisions and the lack of oversight from public international law institutions [8].
2. **Shift in Power Dynamics:** The expansion of ILP for MNCs has altered the balance of power between states and corporations. MNCs, with their vast economic resources, can exert

considerable influence over state policies through their participation in international arbitration proceedings. This has led to criticisms that ISDS provisions privilege corporate interests over those of sovereign states and their citizens.

3. **Accountability and Corporate Governance:** The recognition of MNCs as international legal persons has heightened expectations for their compliance with international norms. As private actors gain rights in the international legal order, they are also subject to greater scrutiny regarding their adherence to human rights, environmental standards, and anti-corruption norms. Future developments in ILP may focus on strengthening accountability mechanisms for private actors in international law [9].

Conclusion

The development of international legal personality in international investment relations marks a significant evolution in the landscape of international law. While the traditional concept of ILP was confined to sovereign states and intergovernmental organizations, the rise of multinational corporations as key players in global investment has necessitated the expansion of ILP to include private actors. This shift reflects broader changes in global governance and raises important questions about the balance of power, accountability, and the future trajectory of international legal norms [10].

As investment relations continue to evolve, so too will the role of ILP in shaping the legal frameworks that govern cross-border economic activities. Addressing the challenges and opportunities posed by this development will be a critical task for scholars, policymakers, and legal practitioners in the years to come.

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